

Linguistic and Cultural Dimensions of Community-Engaged and Collaborative Interpretive Research in Healthcare

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ABSTRACT

Life is a reality that can be both fundamental and challenging at the same time. In this paper, we describe a project in which we seek to improve healthcare processes for persons with serious illness and limited English proficiency in the United States. In this phase of the project, we are working with older adults experiencing dementia whose primary language is Chinese and their family members. We briefly describe the interviews we are conducting, the process of transforming the recordings into usable data, and our iterative and collaborative development of a coding scheme and data analysis process, along with the challenges that we have faced and our approaches to address these.

KEYWORDS

Interviews; transcription; translation; collaborative interpretive analysis; community engaged research

INTRODUCTION

Patients with limited-English proficiency (LEP) experience significant inequities in healthcare (Berdahl & Kirby, 2019; Divi et al., 2007; Karliner et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2011) within the United States (US). In the context of serious illnesses such as dementia, patients with LEP and their families have an inadequate understanding of diagnosis and prognosis, experience sub-optimal communication, and report poor symptom management at the end of life (Arriaza et al., 2011; Butow et al., 2013; Norris et al., 2005; Pham et al., 2008; Silva et al., 2016; Spruyt, 1999; Thornton et al., 2009). Palliative care provides a way to improve quality of life by supporting effective patient-provider communication (Hines et al., 2011; van der Steen et al., 2014), but is under-utilized by patients with LEP and their families. Our study seeks to improve palliative care for older adults with Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias (ADRD) and LEP by identifying barriers to palliative care for patients, families, clinicians, systems, and in the community. The team includes students and others with training in academic research, people who work with community-based organizations, and multilingual persons. One particular challenge of the study is that data will be collected in four different languages/dialects (Spanish, Mandarin Chinese, Cantonese, and Vietnamese). In the current phase of our study, we are working with Chinese communities in the US. In this paper, we will briefly describe our interview research and our approach to data preparation and analysis, including challenges and proposed solutions. We hope our experiences can stimulate discussions concerning challenges and considerations in collaborative community-engaged research with linguistic and cultural dimensions.

INTERVIEW STUDY

We are conducting qualitative research with older adults who experience memory problems and their families. Key parts of the interview include: 1) daily life; 2) healthcare experiences; and 3) the information and support that they may need for decision making and caregiving. Currently, interviews are being conducted in either Mandarin Chinese or Cantonese, and they last approximately one hour. We outsource the interview transcription and translation to a third-party provider, and then perform post-production review upon delivery of the transcription and translation. We are just beginning collaborative data analysis.

APPROACHES, CHALLENGES, STRATEGIES...

We employed a general inductive approach to data analysis involving data preparation, close reading of the text, creation of categories, and continuing revision and refinement of the category system (Thomas, 2006). We describe the challenges encountered in two parts, data preparation and data analysis.

Data Preparation

We have encountered several challenges thus far in data preparation. Our current process is as follows: first, we send interview recordings to a third-party provider for transcription and translation. After receiving the transcription and

translation, we randomly sample sections of the recording to assess the quality of the transcription. If there are significant issues with the recording, we may choose to watch the entire recording and make corrections as needed.

As we have engaged in this process, we have encountered various challenges and questions. For example, though our initial approach was to employ a standardized procedure of moving from the recording to a verbatim transcription and then followed by translation, one research team member brought up the point that she could go faster listening to the audio and translating straight to English, bypassing the Chinese step, due to her greater fluency in English. Ultimately, we opted to retain the step of having a Chinese transcript to facilitate (potentially) greater ease of verification by data analysis team members who could then compare deidentified Chinese transcripts to equivalent English translations if needed, as opposed to consulting recordings containing identifiable information.

However, this comment raises the question of what the recording to translation protocol should be for mixed teams in which team members' stronger and weaker languages may differ. Our current solution affords some flexibility, as we now seek to have the Chinese and English be perceived as "equivalent" by the translation checker, though they may achieve this by having both the Chinese and English juxtaposed while listening to the audio (as opposed to simply checking the Chinese against the English). In addition, we leverage the teams' collective expertise by involving other team members on passages that could have different connotations depending on the translation.

Owing to the particular context of this research, we observed challenges in translation including but not limited to factual errors, discontinuities in the narrative which may be due to cognitive impairment, and issues in capturing a concept with culturally imbued meanings, e.g., "My daughter is extremely filial." While at face value, a literal translation may not be difficult, even the word order may be significant. For example, consider the following:

Whether my daughter or the government will pays for it, I will hire a caregiver at my home.

- *The caregiver will take care of him for some time during the day. For the remaining time of the day, I will take care of him.*
- *I take care of him part of the day, the caregiver takes care of him part of the day.*

The first bullet was the original translation we received from the third party provider; the second reflects the order the participant used to explain, hypothetically, how she would care for her husband if needed. While on its own, the word order reversal may seem insignificant, taken into the context of the participant's entire interview, in which she is adamant that people should not rely on the government to take care of their spouses, the word order is significant. These two examples illustrate text in which the cultural and political context are critical, and interviewing participants in their primary language and performing translation could lead to a richer interpretation.

Often in this type of research, we may outsource translations to a third party. As extant literature has observed, the process of translation may remain "invisible" and be assumed to be an objective process, despite the act of interpretation that inadvertently occurs (Wong & Poon, 2010). We suggest reviewing potential translation issues with analysts so that they can help ensure data quality. Another possibility for increasing analysts' awareness of challenges might be to engage them in the transcription and translation process.

Different translators may have different perspectives on the task. Some may see it as simply a task to be completed; others may see the process as a way to know the language and people more viscerally. A question may arise concerning the extent to which a team should pursue data assessment. In the above example, the difference though conceptually significant, could also require effort that may not be reasonable within the constraints of the project. In addition, catching these types of issues while taking care not to introduce new errors may require significantly more resources. We have sought to weigh the potential benefits of this additional effort against the potential costs, which could be a potential area of difference of opinion within the team.

Data Analysis

While continuing to conduct interviews, we have begun our initial stages of data analysis. Our data analysis team comprises six persons of varying disciplinary backgrounds and lived experience, levels of experience in our fields and with qualitative coding, and different levels of language fluency and familiarity. Such diversity has made it easier to look at issues from different angles, but also poses the challenge of how to develop common ground. We began by independently coding the transcripts and then sharing our coding schemes and coded excerpts with one another. One researcher compiled a starter list of salient codes into a shared document (based on the initially contributed codes) and encouraged team members to add codes. We engaged in iterative discussions to develop a hierarchical code structure and also performed additional literature review relevant to emergent topics from the interview. Based on the literature review, individual team members focused on topics of interest to themselves, adding definitions and examples, which we then discussed and continued to refine in team meetings.

One challenge that we have grappled with in developing the code structure is the question of when a theme should be a high-level category as opposed to a sub- or child code subsumed under a parent code. For example, in the case of social support, we could have it exist on its own. In this case, to better reflect social support in relation to the experiencer, we decided to subsume it under the parent category “older adult,” and also have an identical code subsumed under “family” pertaining to family members. Another example is language barriers. Do we approach this as a high-level category, with sub-codes having to do with different contexts (e.g., patient-provider communication, family dynamics) or have sub-codes of language barriers under each of these concepts? We have been discussing questions such as these collectively to decide on a schema that best reflects the goals of the research.

In the next phase of data analysis, each transcript will be assigned to two coders who will independently code the transcripts. In addition, we may seek to pair a native speaker of Chinese and a non-native speaker of Chinese for each transcript. The reasoning for doing so is that there may be aspects of the language or behavior described in the transcript which has cultural influences that one or the other coder may be more attuned to due to differences in background and/or language. We plan to dialogue and resolve discrepancies by consensus.

We are employing a collective document for brainstorming and schema development. This document includes an index which enables us to quickly jump to sections of interest and organization of the document as it grows over time. Important sections of this document include: links to the different data structures/files, a section for questions/thoughts on topics and procedures, and a section for collaborative development of the coding scheme. In the subsequent sections, we reflect on our experiences in the different voices of our team members to tell the story of our collective journey.

PERSPECTIVES ON CODEBOOK DEVELOPMENT

Leveraging Diverse Areas of Expertise in Codebook Development

SC: Due to the diverse academic backgrounds of the coders, our perspectives and areas of emphasis during the coding process vary. Team members with an information technology background tend to generate codes regarding participants' methods and sources of information acquisition. Those with a medical background tend to delve more deeply into health-related aspects in their interpretations. When assembling a team with members from various domains, the resulting codes and thematic focus exhibit a heightened level of comprehensiveness and diversity.

Iterative Discussion with Examples

XR: I think with iterative discussion, the coding schemes are gradually improving. At the stage of adding definitions and examples, the coder team found ambiguous codes and duplicate codes across groups. This process is very helpful in identifying potential problems of the current code structure. If it's a subcode within a code group, providing an example will be helpful for the group to approve. If it's better to create a new code group, providing the definition for team approval will be beneficial to avoid duplication with other code groups.

Dialoguing to Improve Code Structure

JL: One part of the coding that has been particularly interesting is despite the varying codes that the coders identified, there was a significant amount of overlap in themes and patterns. To address the issue of redundancy, we added definitions and examples and clarified groupings and their subsumed concepts, eventually leading to further streamlining of the coding scheme. We also discussed some challenges that came up while finding applicable examples. For instance, one of the codes we had developed was emotional support for older adults and finding a relevant example for that code led to several discussions, which resulted in creating additional codes (e.g., non-physical support) and re-arranging other code groups (e.g., social networks and social support). These discussions further enhanced our understanding of these concepts and how they could be related.

Integration of Literature Review in Codebook Development

FA: Developing the coding scheme was somewhat challenging after the initial coding of the transcript highlighting concepts. Figuring out the various concepts and arranging them in a structure by appropriately grouping them seemed rather daunting. However, with input from the lead researcher and ideas from other coders, we continued building the coding scheme. To understand these concepts in the coding scheme better and have a deeper understanding, we were assigned different concepts to review. Reviewing literature helped immensely in understanding these codes not just at the manifest level but also at the latent level, to what lies under these phenomena. It was an eye-opening process as it made it easier to view these concepts in their entirety.

REFLECTIONS ON WORK PROCESSES

Task Assignment

SC: Based on the team members' backgrounds and the codes we propose, organizing appropriate task assignments is of paramount importance and can lead to enhanced work efficiency. The allocation of specific thematic

responsibilities to each individual facilitates the definition of codes and the provision of illustrative examples. This procedural approach notably enhances the advancement of discussions. Team members can actively interact with the codes through the expression of their opinions, indicating concurrence or dissent. Furthermore, in instances where explicit guidelines are furnished, this methodology fosters an elevated level of operational efficiency.

Having a Shared Workspace

FA: In qualitative analysis, codes can be used to capture essences, which in turn can be clustered into categories to represent meaning (Saldaña, 2013). For our study, we developed categories collaboratively through an iterative process with an interdisciplinary team of coders who bring an array of perspectives to the process and discussions. Working collaboratively definitely has several advantages, like integrating numerous perspectives, observations, and outlooks, but it is also not free of challenges like coordinating diverse interpretations and managing personal biases.

One of the most surprising elements of this process has been how the single collaborative document has worked so well in becoming our shared workspace and how it has been designed and maintained. The document helps guide our discussions and is easy to follow while tracking the complete analysis process. Instead of shuffling between different documents, tracking everything in a single place has been easier to operate. It helps maintain transparency as we can follow everyone's work and contributions. We continue to develop the analysis process using the document during our team meetings, with each member able to contribute and suggest ideas pertaining to the background or area of work they were assigned. That way, it also allows every member to talk more about their approach, ideas, and contributions, pose questions and concerns, and get feedback from others. It generates an equitable method of discussion and style of conversation where all voices are expressed and heard. As we proceed with coding and analyzing more transcripts, one way to increase understanding of each other's coding approach or the analysis process can be by starting the memoing process. It can be a flexible process where coders can note ideas, thoughts, opinions, and assumptions to elucidate discussion without the idea of having any right or wrong answers. The thoughts can be ambiguous or even vague. Still, documenting them can help better understand the coding process and categorization of the concepts, which can eventually be helpful while writing reports.

Discursive Environment

SC: Frequently, within the domain of qualitative analysis, there isn't a binary categorization of right or wrong answers. In such contexts, the establishment of an open-minded and respectful discussion environment plays a pivotal role in elucidating complexities and eliciting multifaceted viewpoints. This collaborative and inclusive atmosphere cultivates an environment conducive to the exploration of nuances and the synthesis of diverse perspectives, ultimately enriching the depth and breadth of the analysis process.

REFLECTIONS ON POSITIONALITY AND TEAM DYNAMICS

For many/all members of the team, there are aspects of the research that resonate deeply with us. In the case of qualitative research, there is a need to consider one's positionality. While this may be thought of in terms of whether one is an insider or an outsider to a community, Dwyer and Buckle (2009) argue that this view is too simplistic. Indeed, for each of us there are ways in which we may sometimes feel connected to the work, but also differences. For example, some of us may share a common language, but does that mean that we share cultural or life histories? On the flip side, perhaps we do not share a common language or cultural background, but rather, aspects of an interviewee's story resonate with us in terms of the challenges of caregiving or problem solving about serious illness. The mixed composition of our team has facilitated dialogue with respect to this dimension, and we hope to continue to explore ways to perform research collaboratively with this in mind.

In any team effort, power differentials may play unseen roles that affect both the research and the experiences of the parties with an interest in the research. Extant literature has argued that equal partnership, along with understanding of each other's positions, is critical (Somekh, 1994). While in principle we agree, there may be differences in perceived power and expectations which parties may hold and others may not be aware of. We believe that developing an open discursive environment, with different mechanisms enabling people to contribute in ways that are meaningful for them, can give rise to research that is both more meaningful to the individuals involved and more impactful. However, we recognize that despite these mechanisms, continual dialogue, efforts from all parties, and a shared understanding based on time are still needed.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have shared challenges we faced in working on a highly collaborative, multilingual qualitative research project. Working in mixed teams involving healthcare providers, information scientists, and students, and of varying linguistic and cultural backgrounds can result in a richer analysis, but also present its own challenges. We have presented some of our approaches and we look forward to feedback from the workshop audience.

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